

Cyber Threat Intelligence meets the Analytic Tradecraft

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The volumes and sophistication of cyber threats in today's cyber threat landscape have risen to levels where automated quantitative tools for Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) have become an indispensable part in the cyber defense arsenals. The AI and cyber security research communities are producing novel automated tools for CTI that quickly find their ways into commercial products. However, the quality of such automated intelligence products is being questioned by the intelligence community. Cyber security operators are forced to complement the automated tools with costly and time-consuming human intelligence analysis in order to improve the quality of the end product. For improving the quality, it has been suggested that researchers should incorporate methods from traditional intelligence analysis into the quantitative algorithms. This article presents a novel approach to cyber intelligence analysis called AMBARGO, which takes the inherent ambiguity of evidence into account in the analysis, using the Choquet integral, in formalizing the re-evaluation of evidence and hypotheses made by human analysts. The development of AMBARGO revolves around a cyber attribution use case, one of the hardest problems in CTI. The results of our evaluating experiments show that the robustness of AMBARGO outperforms state-of-the-art quantitative approaches to CTI in the presence of ambiguous evidence and potentially deceptive threat actor tactics. AMBARGO has thus the potential to fill a gap in the CTI state-of-the-art, which currently handles ambiguity poorly. The findings are also confirmed in a large-scale realistic experimental setting based on data from an APT campaign obtained from the MITRE ATT&CK Framework.

CCS Concepts: • **Security and privacy** → **Systems security** • **Social and professional topics** → *Malware / spyware crime* • **Computing methodologies** → **Vagueness and fuzzy logic** • **Information systems** → **Clustering and classification**; *Similarity measures*;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Cyber threat intelligence, intelligence analysis, APT attribution, aggregation, ambiguity

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1 Introduction

According to the Diamond Model of Intrusion [11], a cyber threat consists of (i) an adversary with intent and motivation, (ii) a victim, (iii) a set of adversary capabilities, and (iv) vulnerabilities in the technical infrastructure of the victim. The four components are related in a way that can be depicted by the shape of a diamond (Figure 1). The model conveys that a cyber threat requires a connection between the adversary and the victim via vulnerabilities in the infrastructure of the victim and the capabilities of the adversary.

Traditionally, computer system security, and generally cyber security, has been managed largely by passive measures, such as blocking traffic and patching vulnerabilities, making it harder for an attacker to connect to the victim using its capabilities to attack via unpatched infrastructure.

There is however a rapid increase in the frequency of cyber threats, with attacks that are becoming increasingly advanced and menacing, posing a challenge to traditional cyber security. For example, polymorphic malware and **Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs)** are making traditional passive measures less successful in both detecting and preventing the attacks from happening [46]. For this reason, system administrators need to find other ways of mitigating cyber attacks. According to the Diamond model [11], this means focusing the efforts on the adversary and its capabilities rather than on one's own vulnerabilities. However, information about the adversary and its capabilities is not necessarily readily available. The adversary has an incentive to obfuscate as much as possible about its identity, intent, capabilities, and operations. And moreover, there are many ways of hiding through encryption, anonymization, and deception. At the best, useful information about the adversary and an attack can potentially become available incrementally as an adversary operation progresses. This is where **Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI)** comes in. CTI is a variety of intelligence products aimed for helping at understanding and preventing both ongoing and potential future cyber attacks. Examples of such intelligence products, also called **Indicators of Compromise (IOC)**, range from so-called low-level IOCs such as discovery of file-names, hostnames, IP-addresses, and file fingerprints, to high-level IOCs such as cyber attribution; attacker **Tactics, Tools, and Procedures (TTP)**; and cyber situational awareness. The success of CTI stems from its ability to address several needs from the **intelligence community (IC)**, such as efficient intelligence sharing [10, 36, 54] and reducing information overload [4, 48, 54]. This allows overcoming several potential intelligence failures due to not having, for example, shared the right information in the right time to the right people [42], or drowning in too much information of questionable relevance [72].

Academic and commercial state-of-the-art in CTI is dominated by application of statistical and **machine learning (ML)** algorithms [58, 59, 65]. For example, **Natural Language Processing (NLP)** is applied in cyber attribution [52, 55] and automatic extraction of IOCs from unstructured text in threat intelligence reports [29]; Deep learning is applied in cyber attribution [57] and threat detection [15]; Statistical ML approaches, such as anomaly detection, Random Forests, and Support Vector Machines, have also been successfully applied in the field [15, 34, 74]. Recently, researchers have started investigating the use of Large Language Models in the cyber security domain [75]. These data-driven approaches are able to learn patterns in data from a great variety of sources (such as network traffic and host logs) to create statistical and computational models used for predicting, detecting, attributing, and classifying cyber attacks with increasingly high precision. The approaches are generally compared and judged based on their accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores, which, for the state-of-the-art approaches, typically range in the very upper-most percentiles.

Despite the success stories, and recent advances with ML and **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, CTI has however been criticized by the intelligence community for the poor quality of CTI products [7, 44, 51, 72]. The CTI product suffers from an opaqueness where neither evidence nor hypotheses

Fig. 1. Diagram representing the Diamond Model of Intrusion Analysis as described by Caltagirone et al. [11], visualized by the authors.

can be re-visited and re-evaluated during an intelligence investigation. The ability to re-visit and re-evaluate evidence and hypotheses is a prerequisite for high quality intelligence [27]. Oosthoek and Doerr point out that data-driven CTI in general neither allows verification of data sources nor challenging hypothesis, mindsets, and interpretations of evidence [51].

The authors argue that a possible explanation is that IOCs come from commercial vendors with little incentive to reveal its sources [51]. One way of tackling the opaqueness of IOCs and the problem with the low quality of automated CTI is to employ human intelligence analysts who can leverage CTI as an aid in the traditional hypothesis driven intelligence analysis. Indeed, in the case of cyber intelligence, it can be argued that the aid of computational tools is essential for keeping up with the high volumes and paces of incoming data. Mandiant describes, for example, a combination where human analysts can use the output from quantitative cyber attribution algorithms as an aid in the traditional intelligence analysis craft [41]. In another example, Jadidi and Lu [31] suggest a method where human analysts are involved in analyzing computationally generated hypotheses.

Oosthoek and Doerr suggest that an alternative way of improving the quality of the CTI product is specifically to improve the algorithms used for automation:

“CTI has already contributed toward increased computer security, but [...] should not address its challenges by adding more technology. They rather need to be informed by the work on intelligence analysis and methodology, also referred to as analytical tradecraft” [51]

In this article, we present AMBARGO, a framework aiming at answering the research question of how the quality of CTI can be improved through such a combination of traditional intelligence analysis and CTI.

We take the two points made above as points of departure for our analysis. First, we read into Oosthoek and Doerr’s suggestion that we should incorporate methods from the traditional tradecraft into CTI. Second, we consider that many commercial cyber security vendors employ human analysts for improving the quality of the intelligence end products. We ask ourselves: what is it that human analysts do that brings both value and quality to the intelligence product?

Human analysts are trained to constantly challenge their investigations for finding alternative hypotheses that could explain given evidence or events of interest [27]. For doing this, human intelligence analysts use their ability to extract meaning and ramifications of *incomplete*, *ambiguous*, and potentially *deceptive* information [27]. This is an area of expertise where quantitative algorithms perform poorly because of their need for large volumes of high-quality data. In this article, we aim at bridging this gap by formalizing two particular aspects of traditional intelligence analysis that have to do with incomplete and ambiguous evidence:

- Upon arrival of new evidence or when forming new hypotheses, re-visit old evidence and hypotheses for verification and for potential re-evaluation (Formalized in Definition 1);
- Systematically keep track of seen evidence in order to be able to go back for re-evaluation (Formalized in Section 4.3.1).

The two principles play central roles in the structured analytic technique called *Analysis of Competing Hypotheses* (ACH) [53], widely used in traditional intelligence analysis. ACH requires exhaustive enumeration and evaluation of both evidence and hypotheses. To meet this requirement, analysts need to be able to find alternative hypotheses from given evidence and re-evaluate hypotheses in the light of new interpretations of evidence [27]. The main reason for re-visiting and keeping track of evidence and hypotheses is that ambiguous evidence may have been misinterpreted or mis-evaluated in early stages of an investigation. Moreover, as an investigation progresses, new evidence may invalidate old interpretations, and new hypotheses may revive previously discarded evidence.

The concept of ambiguity is in this article taken to mean an ontological uncertainty about, or indecision of, what a piece of evidence means. This is different from epistemic uncertainty (as in probability) where evidence has a crisp, but unknown, meaning. Vagueness, or fuzziness, is closely related and deals with uncertainty due unclear boundaries between evidence [63]. In the cyber domain, ambiguity stems not only from the inherent incompleteness of the evidence (due, for example, to evasive and deceptive tactics on the part of threat actors), but in particular also from the incompleteness and uncertainty in the *process of evaluating evidence*. As an example, consider malware code analysis where the task is to decide whether a forensic code sample belongs to one malware family or another. Such decisions are often made based on similarity between the forensic sample and code from a known malware family, where similarity most often is defined as a closest match, or a match above some threshold [66]. Decisions of membership made on such grounds may be subject for revision. For example, if the investigator decides to run a second analysis, with slightly different decision criteria, or perhaps more thorough, the analysis may result in a different membership decision. Ambiguity of evidence arises on the part of the consumer of the malware analysis, as he or she may lack information of the analysis procedures and the evidence used for producing the analysis result. In intelligence analysis, the analyst manages ambiguity by collecting as much evidence as possible for arriving at consistent interpretations of the potentially ambiguous evidence. AMBARGO emulates this way of dealing with ambiguous evidence by aggregating the weights from all possible interpretations of evidence in the AMBARGO integral (Definition 3).

The main point we are making in this article is that the state-of-the-art data-driven ML and statistics based approaches to CTI are not well-suited for handling ambiguous and potentially deceptive data and evidence. This is due to their reliance on the so-called *additivity* of the probability measure. One consequence of additivity is that evidence can have only one meaning, which is contrary to the needs of intelligence analysis. AMBARGO is based on a *super-additive* measure that allows evidence to have several interpretations, which is the key to formalizing the two principles of ACH described above.

AMBARGO is evaluated through a statistical experiment based on a real-world cyber attribution use case adapted from Mandiant [41]. We evaluate AMBARGO first in the sense of its super-additive measure versus the fuzzy and the additive measures, verifying that our formalization of ambiguity has a potential practical impact. For verifying scalability and real-world applicability of AMBARGO, we perform further experiments on a large-scale realistic dataset and with forensic samples based on the APT29 campaign Operation Ghost. Moreover, to ensure that our findings hold more generally, we compare, in the large-scale experiment, AMBARGO with a range of state-of-the-art advanced ML algorithms common in the academic CTI literature.

The contributions of this article are

- The introduction of the cyber intelligence analysis approach AMBARGO, which successfully incorporates traditional intelligence analysis into CTI.
- The concept of *intelligence arguments* as a representation schema for reasoning about cyber intelligence arguments, in both CTI and traditional intelligence analysis.

- By experimentation, we show that AMBARGO performs robustly in settings with ambiguous and potentially deceptive evidence, where state-of-the-art is known to perform poorly.

The article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we review related work with respect to incorporating methods from traditional intelligence analysis into CTI and to related applications in cyber attribution. Section 3 gives background in traditional intelligence analysis, CTI, and Fuzzy Integration. In Section 4, we first formulate the running cyber attribution use case. Then we define the AMBARGO approach, in particular how it represents ambiguous evidence using intelligence arguments; how it incorporates principles from the analytic tradecraft; and how it can be used in real-world applications (the AMBARGO translation and integral). In Section 5 we set up a statistical experiment on which AMBARGO is applied to evaluate its usefulness, scalability, and applicability. In Section 6, we give an account of the computational complexity of AMBARGO, outline an architecture and discuss potential implementation. Section 7 discusses limitations of AMBARGO. Section 8 is the conclusion.

2 Related Work

Despite the criticism of the low quality of the CTI product, and the urge for improved methods in the CTI production, there has been very few approaches incorporating methods from traditional intelligence analysis into the CTI production. Among the approaches that do, Sauerwine et al. [61] review the state-of-the-art in cyber intelligence sharing platforms, noting that the platforms, in general, share merely threat data rather than the promised actionable intelligence. Their approach takes its departure in the traditional Intelligence Cycle [39] to identify requirements on cyber intelligence sharing for enabling production of actionable intelligence. They identify functional processes in the Intelligence Cycle that are missing from cyber intelligence sharing platforms and thus limiting the usefulness of such platforms in intelligence analysis. This addresses a functional mismatch between CTI and traditional analysis, while it does not address the more serious criticism of today's CTI to not be able to handle ambiguous evidence the way needed for traditional analysis. In another approach also using the intelligence cycle, da Silva et al. [40] aim for improving the quality of CTI by presenting IOCs with enriched contextual information. However, da Silva et al. consider only relevance, accuracy, and completeness of the data, without addressing the call from the Intelligence Community about improving the quality by allowing the analyst to challenge interpretations and consider alternative hypotheses. Contrary to these two approaches, we aim with AMBARGO to address exactly the shortcomings, with respect to ambiguity, of today's CTI that impede the workflow of traditional analysis.

Jadidi and Lu [31] present a framework for cyber threat hunting that incorporates the use of the Diamond Model of intrusion [11], the Cyber Kill Chain[®] [30], and the MITRE ATT&CK[®] Framework [47] for generating hypotheses about suspected events, triggered by relevant CTI obtained in a first phase. The generated hypotheses are subsequently used for producing the final CTI product. The hypothesis generation is performed in a semi-automated fashion, allowing human analyst involvement in the critical part of the analysis. While this approach both ensures a better quality product and incorporates the analytic tradecraft, it does not address the main issue of our article. The focus in our article is to address computational approaches that fully automate also the steps where Jadidi and Lu allow human intelligence analysis (i.e., in hypothesis generation). Our main issue is to address the problems that arise when such steps rely on the ambiguity of evidence while the computational approach lacks representational power for ambiguous evidence.

Devlin [16] presents a non-classical mathematical framework to formalize contextual reasoning in military intelligence, from the ground up. He is able to capture both human judgment and contextual dependence. Devlin's work is more closely related to our work than the previously mentioned. The difference between Devlin's work and AMBARGO is that Devlin focuses on how

to represent the *context* in which judgment on ambiguous evidence can be resolved through disambiguation. In our article, we take the perspective of the intelligence analyst and focus on the *ambiguity* of evidence, where different (possibly inconsistent) judgments represent equally valid interpretations of the evidence.

With respect to cyber attribution, many authors in CTI obtain a first stage of attribution based on technical artifacts and machine learning techniques, recognizing the need for and implementing a second stage where the model is enriched with contextual information. For example, Xiang et al. [73] use a probability based approach to obtain attack characterizations based on (low-level) IOCs. They recognize that in order to improve attribution, the characterization should be enriched with contextual data obtained from commercial CTI vendors. Ren et al. [55] provide a unified framework for expressing and storing context and attack details in knowledge graphs, to be used both in training for simulation of attacks and in operational settings. Related to this, Mavroeidis et al. [45] integrate CTI with contextual attacker information in an ontology for providing support for intelligence analysts. However, while these approaches address context, they do not address ambiguity and deception potentially present in neither the IOCs nor in the contextual data.

Fuzzy approaches to attribution (e.g., Alaeiylan et al. [1], Haddadpajouh et al. [25], Thonnard et al. [68]) improve on additive approaches (e.g., probabilistic, statistical, and machine learning approaches) in the respect of capturing similarities of traces across several classes (i.e., vagueness), paying a price in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall. The underlying machinery associates a given trace with several APTs, which necessitates a so-called defuzzification step for a unique final attribution. In a related approach, Thonnard et al. [69] use an ordered weighted average to gain more control over the final aggregation and attribution. AMBARGO differs from the fuzzy approaches by treating class overlap as alternative valid interpretations (i.e., ambiguity) rather than as vagueness.

Several authors (e.g., Applebaum et al. [6], Nunes et al. [50]) propose approaches to cyber attribution using Argumentation Frameworks [19]. The advantages of these approaches are that they can handle inconsistent and incomplete evidence as well as real-time dynamic updates and non-monotonic inference. Argumentation frameworks are well-suited for formalizing the attribution process, but have a disadvantage due to the extensive simplifications needed for expressing the real-world problem in terms of logical theories. AMBARGO shares the ability to handle inconsistencies, and devises a form of arguments that avoids the same extent of simplifications.

3 Background

3.1 Intelligence Analysis

Decision makers consume a product called *intelligence*, which is timely, actionable, and relevant knowledge about an operating environment and its actors [44]. The activities for producing intelligence are collectively called *intelligence analysis*. A common model for intelligence analysis is the Intelligence Cycle [39], describing the analysis in five phases: *direction*, *collection*, *preprocessing*, *analysis*, and *dissemination*. The Intelligence Cycle has been criticized for not representing the actual workflows of intelligence analysis [7, 20, 28], and in particular for not reflecting the empirical and data-driven nature of CTI [61].

Intelligence is typically requested on matters, for example in early stages of a crisis, where information is incomplete, ambiguous, and potentially deceptive. In order to understand and explain observed events, the intelligence analyst must rely on mental models and heuristic shortcuts to form hypotheses based on best efforts [27]. Due to human mental limitations, such mental models often lead to misjudgment of evidence, and the analyst must therefore continuously review and re-evaluate assumptions and evidence throughout an investigation [27]. The meaning of, potentially

ambiguous, evidence is interpreted in larger contexts, also called *lenses*, based on the analyst's own experiences and assumptions [44]. In order to handle the inherent uncertainty in the analysis process, a common way is to use **Structured Analytic Techniques (SAT)** [53]. SAT is a collection of analytic tools for minimizing bias and cognitive errors throughout the analysis process [24, 43]. In this article, we will focus in particular on one analytic tool for hypothesis generation: *Analysis of Competing Hypotheses*.

3.2 Cyber Threat Intelligence

CTI is an intelligence product where the operating environment is cyberspace. CTI differs from ordinary intelligence products, especially with respect to the timing dimension. In contrast to traditional operating environment where threats may be detected long before they materialize, a cyber threat can materialize at the same time as it is detected. Moreover, traces of a cyber attack may vanish long before forensic collection of evidence begins, or even before the attack has been detected. The major difference between CTI and ordinary intelligence products is that CTI is a data-driven and quantitative product [22], whereas traditional intelligence is mainly hypothesis driven.

The Cyber Kill Chain [30] is a model that describes the phases that an attacker must complete during a cyber attack. The phases are: *reconnaissance*; *weaponization*; *delivery*; *exploitation*; *installation*; *command and control*; *actions and objectives*. Each phase can be uniquely characterized and detected through cyber surveillance and intelligence analysis. When a adversary cyber attack has been detected, determining its active phase helps mitigating the attack through the choice of appropriate countermeasures.

The Diamond model [11] is a framework for modeling cyber intrusions in terms of four atomic features: *adversary*, *victim*, *capability* and *infrastructure*; and in terms of a number meta-features such as timestamps and resources used. The model is used for linking events based on common features. For example by matching the timestamp and geographic location of a purchase of hardware with the whereabouts of a suspected adversary. By forming chains of events linked through their features, the analyst can build a compelling story that forms the final cyber intelligence product.

Indicators of Compromise (IOCs) are technical artifacts that when found in computer systems or in logs indicate an ongoing or completed attack. There are also behavioral traces that can reveal **Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs)** that can be associated with attacks and attackers. Both IOCs and TTPs are used in cyber attribution.

Cyber attribution is an advanced CTI product, described in [66] by the 4C model: *collect*, *cluster*, *charge*, and *communicate*. Collection and clustering of attack data (i.e., IOCs and TTPs) can be automated using data analysis and ML, and may contribute with low-level attribution in the form of, e.g., country of origin of the attack. A more valuable form of attribution is obtained when a group or individual can be charged with an attack, which at present cannot be achieved without human analysis. The charging process builds on aggregating the collected and clustered attack data into judgment of attribution, and this is the aspect which is addressed by AMBARGO.

Steffens [66] considers evidence in terms of dimensions, for example *malware family*, *attack infrastructure*, and *geopolitical analysis*. Having data from only one dimension results in low confidence attribution, while having data from three or more dimensions gives a higher confidence. Attack data from several dimensions can be enough for uniquely identifying a threat actor, and in such cases the attack data forms a so-called *intrusion set*.

Cyber attribution is an important aspect of cyber defense, especially as a deterrence [9]. Cyber attribution has also a political aspect partly for preventing high costs in cases of misattribution, and partly because attribution can be used as way of coercing or in negotiation [56].

3.3 Additivity and Fuzzy Integration

A common computational task is to classify a datapoint (e.g., a forensic sample) f to belong to one of the classes C_1, \dots, C_n , based on a set of information sources S_1, \dots, S_m , where each source S_i gives a support $s_{ij} \geq 0$ that f belongs to C_j . In order to come to a conclusion of to which class f belongs, the support values need to be aggregated into one single value. The dominant and most common way to do this, for example in probability theory, is to compute the weighted average for all s_{ij} for each class C_j , and then select as classification the class for which the weighted average is the largest [71]. The probabilistic approach with weighted averages assumes that the information sources are independent. This assumption can lead to misclassifications in the presence of dependencies between the information sources [33].

A typical use case where the information sources exhibit dependencies is in the presence of ambiguity in the sources, exactly as in the topic for this article.

In this article, we define the fuzzy integral in terms of the discrete Choquet integral with a super-additive measure [14], which is a common approach for dealing with ambiguous data [64]. In the following we give enough intuition for these concepts to follow the rest of the article, where the intuition is based on material in [64]. The discrete Choquet integral is defined in terms of classes C_1, \dots, C_n and information sources S_1, \dots, S_m as described above.

We shall first define the concepts *additivity* and *super-additivity*, which are referred to throughout the article. Form the set Ω of all subsets of the set $\{S_1, \dots, S_m\}$, and define a measure g on Ω such that $g(A) \leq g(B)$ whenever $A \subseteq B$ for $A, B \in \Omega$ and such that $g(\emptyset) = 0$. For disjoint A and B , define the *interaction constant* λ for the measure g by the expression $g(A \cup B) = g(A) + g(B) + \lambda g(A)g(B)$. If $\lambda = 0$, then g is called *additive* (as for example the common probability measure). For $\lambda > 0$, the measure is said to be *super-additive* (which is what AMBARGO and the fuzzy approaches in this article use); and for $\lambda < 0$, g is said to be *sub-additive*.

The Choquet integral requires that we can determine the measure $g(A)$ for any $A \in \Omega$. We utilize a way of inducing (i.e., the Sugeno measure [67]) these measures from assessments of the atomic subsets of Ω . (i.e., $g(\{S_i\})$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$.)

The Choquet integral is defined for a *piece of evidence* e for each class C_j where e is a sequence of support values e_{1j}, \dots, e_{mj} for C_j . Let us assume that the values are ordered so that $e_{1j} \geq \dots \geq e_{mj}$. (If not, re-order them). From the order, we induce a sequence of sets $\{S_1\} \subseteq \{S_1, S_2\} \subseteq \dots \subseteq \{S_1, \dots, S_m\} = \Omega_e$. These subsets are called the *induced capacity* from e , and we denote them as A_1, \dots, A_m such that $A_i = \{S_1, \dots, S_i\}$. Finally, define the super-additive measure \mathcal{G}_λ^r on the sets A_i of the capacity, for some $\lambda > 0$, and where the atomic measure $\mathcal{G}_\lambda^r(\{S_k\})$ is obtained based on some criterion r . The discrete Choquet integral for the evidence e and class C_j is given by

$$H(e, C_j) = \sum_{i=1}^m e_{(i)} (\mathcal{G}_\lambda^r(A_i) - \mathcal{G}_\lambda^r(A_{i-1})).$$

We refer in the sequel to the discrete Choquet integral as the fuzzy integral. We shall also use the notation \mathcal{G}_λ^r for a super-additive measure throughout the article, with r specified.

4 AMBARGO For Cyber Threat Intelligence

In this section, we develop and introduce AMBARGO, a novel approach to CTI, in the context of a running cyber attribution use case. Section 4.1 identifies sources of ambiguity in the cyber domain. In Section 4.2, we state the attribution problem and discuss the short-comings of state-of-the-art approaches with respect to their common feature of relying on the additive probabilistic measures. Section 4.3 presents *intelligence arguments*, our main vehicle for representing ambiguity in the setting of intelligence analysis. In Section 4.4 we present a structure for controlling how intelligence

arguments can be used in cyber reasoning. This is where the Analytic Tradecraft is incorporated into AMBARGO. We here also introduce a method for representing the cyber attribution problem in AMBARGO: the AMBARGO *translation*. Finally, in Section 4.4.2, we define the AMBARGO *Integral*, which is the computational tool for applying AMBARGO on the cyber attribution problem. These components contribute to a workflow where the novel AMBARGO concepts are used for producing CTI based on cyber situational awareness that can be obtained via legacy ML algorithms. The workflow is presented as a diagram in Figure 14, where a potential architecture is discussed.

4.1 Sources of Ambiguity in the Cyber Domain

Ambiguity has several sources in the cyber domain. Like in intelligence analysis in general, cyber intelligence aims at making sense out of ambiguous (and incomplete) information about evolving threats [27]. Moreover, threat actors naturally have incentive to increase the chances that the defender misinterprets traces and signals [26], by injecting ambiguity into their offensive operations through stealthy tactics [21]. In order to make sense of a cyber threat, defenders analyze various traces of threat actor activities, obtained for example through analysis of host and network traffic logs. It is also common that defenders rely on feeds of IOCs and TTPs, possibly shared by other defenders. The traces thus serve the investigator with TTPs and IOCs regarding an attack. For brevity, we use henceforth the collective term IOCs for such traces, considering TTPs as high level IOCs.

Throughout the article, since we are concerned with ambiguity, we consider the point of view of the defender, and we model thus the defender's perception of the attacker behavior. Therefore, we do not assume temporal or causal orders between TTPs or IOCs (as common in the APT literature), since detection and analysis of traces may be out of that order. Moreover, when we later talk of traces of intrusion containing certain numbers of TTPs, it should be understood as the number of TTPs that the defender has perceived. (In practice, the actual number of TTPs are of course unknown). Similarly, when we speak of a TTP being of certain kind, it is the kind perceived by the defender.

We are interested in the ambiguity arising when the defender has limited, or no, insight into the mechanisms with which the IOCs are produced. We call this *inference ambiguity*. A second form of ambiguity is *information ambiguity*, arising with vague indata and is addressed in fuzzy and possibilistic approaches. In inference ambiguity, even with crisp indata, ambiguity may arise as indata is aggregated into a decision or a representation. This is the case when the IOC is derived through a chain of interpretations and when the interpretations not necessarily are conveyed to the end consumer. In the malware example from the introduction, an IOC saying that the forensic code sample belongs to the **remote access tool (RAT)** family PlugX¹ may in fact have been based on an incomplete analysis, or the code sample may have been similar to both PlugX and a second family gh0stRAT² of RATs, but with a small margin it was closer to PlugX. Thus, that the IOC is pointing to PlugX, could be based merely on a misinterpretation. This is exactly the opaqueness of IOCs discussed in the introduction, which contributes to the criticism of CTI coming from the Intelligence Community. It is also this aspect of ambiguity in IOCs we are going to consider in the rest of the article.

The inherent ambiguity of IOCs (or in general, evidence) is handled differently in traditional intelligence analysis and in CTI. In traditional intelligence analysis, the analyst may go back to re-examine the evidence to see whether there is an interpretation not yet considered, or previously

¹<https://attack.mitre.org/software/S0013/>

²<https://attack.mitre.org/software/S0032/>

dismissed, that could make sense in the investigation. The possibility to re-examine and verify evidence is a prerequisite for high quality intelligence end products [27].

In CTI however, the handling of ambiguity in IOCs is not by re-visiting evidence (hence the opaqueness) but rather by, as precise and exhaustively as possible, including the best possible conclusions/evidence from the input data into the IOC. As we will see below, the state-of-the-art additive approaches rely on the ability to quantitatively aggregate indata into relevant information that can be used in a final intelligence product. This aggregation step, we argue, is a source of inference ambiguity. The fuzzy approach acknowledges that indata may be ambiguous and applies a super-additive measure to allow evidence to support several possible interpretations. Where fuzzy approaches handle information ambiguity, AMBARGO constructs a way to handle also inference ambiguity, through an integration over all available evidence in one go. While this concept will be formally defined in Definition 4, we can say informally, that this is AMBARGO's way of emulating the intelligence analysis principles of re-evaluating and keeping track of evidence.

4.2 A Cyber Attribution Example and Terminology

We will use an instance of the *cyber attribution problem* as a running example throughout this section. In addition, an extended version of the same use case will be used in Section 5, for illustrating a real-world application of AMBARGO and for evaluating its performance. The cyber attribution problem consists in confidently attributing a cyber attack to a known threat actor. In other words, cyber attribution is a classification problem.

The state-of-the-art for classification problems in cyber security, and in general for *quantitative* CTI, builds mainly on ML and statistical approaches [2, 58, 59]. Zhao et al. [76] use Convolutional Networks and Gao et al. [23] use a Heterogeneous Information Network for threat modeling. The threat intelligence company Mandiant describe a probabilistic model called ATOMIC for cyber attribution [41]. Recently, advanced ML algorithms such as XGBoost have been used for cyber threat detection [5], and ensemble deep neural networks for cyber attribution [32].

While ML-based models dominate the state-of-the-art in CTI, we are more concerned with their common feature of relying on additive probability measures for aggregation. To be precise, we are interested in investigating to what extend the additive feature of state-of-the-art ML approaches to CTI may impede their performance on ambiguous data. For the purpose of implementing an additive approach to be used in the experiments (Section 5), we select Mandiant's probabilistic model ATOMIC [41] as a representative for the additive approaches. Mandiant have also provided detail into how ATOMIC is applied in cyber attribution [41]. In Section 5.6, we make a wider comparison with state-of-the-art ML-based approaches, to verify that no information was lost in focusing on this aspect.

Mandiant [41] describe the common workflow of collecting and collating IOCs and TTPs into sets, called *documents*, based on common features (for example having the same source). Through further analysis, documents are gathered into clusters of documents that are *similar* to each other. When a cluster is stable and sufficiently dissimilar from other clusters, it can sometimes be associated with an APT. Once identified with an APT, the evidence (IOCs and TTPs) in the cluster together form a so-called *intrusion set*. The notion of similarity between documents is central for cyber attribution. In addition to the clustering described above, metrics of similarity is also used in determining to which cluster a new forensic evidence belongs. For formalizing the concept of similarity between documents, Mandiant use the notion of *topics*, reflecting important aspects of the collected evidence. Topics could, for example, be *malware family*, *targeted industry*, *suspected motive*, *techniques*, or the IP-address of known *command and control servers*. Each topic has a number of members, For example, the topic *targeted industry* could have as members "banking", "military", and "transport". What makes cyber attribution challenging is that documents rarely

contain complete or non-ambiguous intrusion sets, due both to the transient nature of evidence in the cyber domain and to stealthy tactics of threat actors.

For the concreteness of the rest of the article, we shall fix some settings and notation. The APTs in our examples will be denoted by APT_1, \dots, APT_k , for some $k > 0$. The clusters will be denoted C_i , where the index i associates the cluster with the i th APT, APT_i . Thus, C_i stands for what is known about APT_i from preceding analysis and surveillance. A collection of such clusters, C_1, \dots, C_k , shall be called an *attribution model*. We define three named *topics*: *malware family*, *targeted industry*, and *potential motive*, for ease of discussions. However, the topic labels are not important, and in the statistical experiments below we will simply define a range $1, \dots, T$ of topics, for some $T > 0$. Each topic has a set of members which we also will denote by ranges of integers. Again, for ease of discussion, we name two members of the malware family topic—PlugX and gh0stRAT, the two remote access tools mentioned above.

With a *forensic sample* f we mean a collection of IOCs, and a forensic sample is meant to correspond to Mandiant’s notion of document. In order to classify f with respect to an attribution model, we must define a metric to compute the distance from f to each of the clusters C_i . In cases with multi-feature elements, it is common to measure the distances for each topic separately, and to aggregate the results of these measurement into a single score. Mandiant use the cosine-similarity measure for creating so-called *topic vectors* for each topic. For example, with respect to an attribution model with k clusters, the topic vector for the topic malware family, would be a vector $d_1, \dots, d_j, \dots, d_k$ of length k , where each d_j is the distance from the sample f to the cluster C_j with respect to the topic malware family.

Mandiant [41] aggregates the count of terms using the TF-IDF algorithm [60] in order to compare the forensic sample with clusters in the attribution model. Without loss of generality, we use the simpler **term-frequency (TF)** score to make a similar statistics. For each topic t and each term t_i in the topic, the TF-score gives the ratio of the count of term t_i and the total number of occurrences of any term t_j in the forensic sample. We stack the topic vectors obtained from a forensic sample into a *forensic matrix* f . For illustration, with three named topics and 10 members each, f could be

$$f = \begin{array}{l} \text{malware} \\ \text{industry} \\ \text{motive} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \left| \begin{array}{cccccccccc} 0.05 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.04 & 0 & 0.18 & 0.73 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.4 & 0 & 0. & 0.7 & 0. & 0.3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.4 & 0 & 0. & 0.7 & 0. & 0.3 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right. \end{array} \quad (1)$$

We shall also write the clusters in the attribution models in a similar way, as *cluster matrices*. For example:

$$C_4 = \begin{array}{l} \text{malware} \\ \text{industry} \\ \text{motive} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \left| \begin{array}{cccccccccc} 0 & 0 & 0.51 & 0 & 0 & 0.38 & 0 & 0 & 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0. & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0. & 0 & 0 & 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.56 & 0. & 0 & 0.1 & 0.1 & 0 & 0.2 & 0 & 0.2 \end{array} \right. \end{array}$$

Attribution is determined by finding the cluster that f resembles the most. This step typically involves an aggregation step, and in [41] the aggregation is made by taking the weighted average of all topic vector distances. Our implementation of the probabilistic algorithm for aggregation and attribution is described in detail in Section 5 where we apply this approach on our use case. Here we will continue by discussing the additive approach from the perspective of ambiguity.

4.2.1 Problem with Additive Approaches in CTI. In this section, we consider the common feature of additivity of the dominant ML and statistics state-of-the-art approaches in CTI. We discussed in Section 3.3 the difference between additive and super-additive measures when it comes to ambiguous data.

Since intelligence analysis deals with ambiguous data, we should expect the additive approaches' inability to handle ambiguity to reflect in the results of applying the additive probabilistic approach in CTI. *We hypothesize that the additive approaches' poor handling of ambiguity may be one of the reasons for the perceived poor quality of the end product in CTI.*

Contrary to our hypothesis, however, the experiments we perform in Section 5 appear to show that the machine learning based probabilistic additive approach we deploy in the experiment handle potentially ambiguous data very well, at least with respect to the traditional metrics accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Given the intelligence community's criticism for the low quality of the CTI intelligence product, we are compelled in this article to dig deeper into the apparent discrepancy between the high evaluation scores of the computational approaches and the need for employing human analysts for improving the quality. Upon digging deeper, we see that the state-of-the-art approaches using additive measures perform well under two strong assumptions.

The first assumption is that the forensic sample is drawn from a distribution similar to the distribution of the data on which the model was trained. The second assumption is that every piece of evidence supports at most one hypothesis (but it may be epistemically uncertain which one). Interestingly, when we apply metrics better suited for intelligence analysis (i.e., measuring the confidence in the attribution, and the discernability of alternative hypotheses), the performance of the additive approach tends to be lower. Moreover, the performance of the additive approach drops even further when we in Section 5 simulate stealthy and deceptive threat actor tactics.

We argue that these two assumptions are unrealistic from the point of view of the defender (recall that we are taking the point of view of the defender), considering stealthy tactics of APTs [35]. The first assumption presupposes that threat actors act in easily predictable manners, which is contrary to the assumed stealthiness and adaptability of APTs [12, 35]. The second assumption is unrealistic in the sense that the defender has access to only incomplete, ambiguous, and potentially deceptive data. This means that the defender must be open for several different interpretations of a piece of evidence, even in the presence of further evidence that favors one of the possible interpretations [27]. For continuing the malware example, it is unrealistic that a forensic sample that bears the characteristics of a RAT would be evidence of either the gh0stRAT or the PlugX families, but not both. The decision on membership could ultimately depend on contextual evidence. Note that evidence of the sample belonging to one family of RATs, need in practice not exclude the possibility of it belonging to another family.

An alternative approach that could be used for handling ambiguous evidence, while being based on additive probabilistic measures, could potentially be provided by **Large Language Models (LLMs)**. However, although LLMs have been applied for reasoning in domains such as medical diagnosis [62] and in general problem solving as well as in complex reasoning tasks [3, 38], they perform poorly on these complex reasoning tasks. LLMs are in general, at present, trained for disambiguating contexts and predict the most likely interpretation of ambiguous terms, which amounts to the second assumption above. Liu et al. [37] perform a systematic test on the most advanced LLMs (as of 2023), for their ability to reason with ambiguous data. The authors test state-of-the-art LLMs to see if they are capable to (i) produce a relevant disambiguation; (ii) recognize ambiguous terms, and (iii) model possible interpretations. The LLMs performed poorly on all three tasks, and much worse than a reference score based on human assessments.

As will be seen in our experiments (Section 5), AMBARGO perform robustly also under the assumption of deceptive tactics, thus alleviating the need for the restrictive assumption of forensic samples being drawn from distribution similar to historical training data. Moreover, the AMBARGO integral (Definition 3) is defined using a super-additive measure, which in practice makes it possible for distinct interpretation or distinct hypotheses to receive support from one and the same piece of evidence. This alleviates the need for the second assumption.

Table 1. Example of a Analytic Matrix, a Central Concept in the Analytic Tradecraft [27]

	Hypothesis 1	Hypothesis 2	Hypothesis 3
evidence A	consistent	consistent	neutral
evidence B	consistent	neutral	inconsistent
evidence C	inconsistent	consistent	inconsistent

4.3 AMBARGO: Intelligence Arguments

AMBARGO is a computational approach to CTI and as such it should consume input and produce an output as a function of its input. That the input to AMBARGO is potentially ambiguous and incomplete has already been established, and the shortcomings of quantitative (probabilistic) methods to represent such data have been discussed in the literature, for example in [17]. This naturally poses a challenge in representation of indata for AMBARGO. However, AMBARGO aims in addition at representing two principles of the analytic tradecraft; namely the ability to revisit an re-evaluate hypotheses and evidence, and as well keeping track of evidence. The construction of AMBARGO is thus further challenged to reflect the human analyst's ability to keep contradictory interpretations of evidence in mind, and to connect evidence and hypotheses in an ongoing iterative procedure where evidence is re-interpreted and hypotheses re-evaluated. Typically, to make sense of one piece of evidence, the analyst is required to interpret further evidence in the context one or more hypotheses [24]. In the example above with determining whether a forensic code sample belongs to one of the malware families PlugX and gh0stRAT, a human intelligence analyst would collect contextual evidence from, e.g., geopolitical events using CTI models such the Cyber Kill Chain [30] or the Diamond Model [11], for additional clues to the code sample family membership.

Similar to Mandiant's computational procedure for attribution (Section 4.2.1), we can see that also human analysts make an aggregation of evidence in deciding for a final set of hypotheses (in our case, a final attribution). Analysts form a so-called Analytic Matrix of collected evidence (for key indicators) along one dimension and hypotheses along the other [27], exemplified in Table 1. The evidence for each key-indicator is evaluated separately and after that each pair of evidence and hypothesis is assessed with respect to how much support the evidence gives to the hypothesis. This assessment is often qualitative or ordinal (*weak*, *neutral*, *strong*), or consistency-based (whether the hypothesis is *consistent*, *inconsistent*, or *independent* with the evidence) [27]. The interesting aspect of the human aggregation is the role played by the interpretation. First of all, the interpretation is not represented in the analytic matrix. However, it plays a decisive role in determining the assessment of consistency between evidence and hypotheses. The aspect of interpretation is, we say here, where ambiguity plays its role in intelligence analysis. First, ambiguous data need to be interpreted to make sense. Second, The final aggregation result depends on how the evidence has been interpreted.

AMBARGO extends the concept of analytic matrix by introducing so-called *intelligence arguments*, which concisely package the notions of *evidence*, *interpretation of evidence*, *hypothesis*, and an *evaluation* of the consistency between hypothesis and evidence. Formally, we define an intelligence argument as a tuple $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$ where x_1 represents a piece of evidence (e.g., the forensic matrix f in the use case below); x_2 represents the interpretation of the evidence (e.g., as we shall use below, a topic/row in the forensic matrix); x_3 represents a hypothesis that may or may not be supported by the evidence and its interpretation; and where x_4 is a consistency judgment (for example as a term in an ordinal scale: *weak*, *neutral*, and *strong*). An example of an intelligence argument from our use case is

The forensic sample, interpreted in terms of malware family membership, consistently supports the hypothesis that APT₁ originated the attack.

4.3.1 Keeping a Record of Evidence. The notion of intelligence arguments allows us to represent ambiguous indata. Typically, an ambiguous evidence e would support two (or more) different hypotheses h_1 and h_2 . This is not a functional relation from evidence to hypotheses. Hence, for a classical mathematical approach, there must be a decision of which hypothesis is to be supported by e before a final decision can be made. In probability theory for example, both hypotheses can have a positive likelihood given evidence e , but for making a decision, statistical inference makes a non-monotonic inference step (e.g., with maximum likelihood) to discard all but the hypothesis with the highest likelihood for enabling the decision.

In AMBARGO, we use the interpretation term (x_2) of the intelligence arguments to enable representation of the ambiguous evidence e by introducing two different interpretations of e in two different intelligence arguments:

$$(e, i_1, h_1, v_1) \quad \text{and} \quad (e, i_2, h_2, v_2), \quad i_1 \neq i_2.$$

The generation of such alternative intelligence arguments is governed by the AMBARGO translation, defined shortly below. Using the translation, no interpretation and no evidence need to be discarded before AMBARGO makes a decision on classification. Instead, all evidence contribute toward the aggregated value of the AMBARGO integral, which is defined on sets of intelligence arguments.

4.4 Reasoning with Intelligence Arguments

In AMBARGO, sets of intelligence arguments represent cyber reasoning. For example, an analytic matrix corresponds to a set of intelligence arguments. The AMBARGO integral (Section 4.4.2) is defined with respect to a measure defined on sets of intelligence arguments. Further, the attribution use case formulated as a set of intelligence arguments.

The connection from sets of intelligence arguments to analytic matrices can informally be described as follows. Let A be a set of intelligence arguments of the form $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$. Then the set H of hypotheses in the analytic matrix can be induced from A by

$$H = \{x_3 \mid x \in A\}$$

The set $E = \{x_1 \mid x \in A\}$ is the set of evidence collected in the investigation. The consistency assessments in the analytic matrix between hypothesis h and evidence e are obtained from $E = \{x_4 \mid (e, _, h, x_4) \in A\}$.

Similarly to how human intelligence analysts use the analytic matrix to reason about cyber attribution, we use sets of intelligence arguments in AMBARGO to aid reasoning and computation. We shall utilize the notion of sets of intelligence arguments to form a relational algebra of intelligence arguments. We incorporate the analytic tradecraft into CTI by imposing formalized principles from the tradecraft as relations defined on sets of intelligence arguments.

In the view of intelligence arguments as terms of a relational algebra, we can impose restrictions on their uses by defining relations on sets of intelligence arguments. As the aim for AMBARGO is to formalize the way human intelligence analysts deal with ambiguous evidence, we want to capture the two ideas of *re-evaluating* previously seen evidence and to *look for alternative* hypotheses.

In order to be able to formulate the two principles, we need first the concept of hypothesis space from traditional intelligence analysis. The hypothesis space consists of the hypotheses that are currently held for true (or plausible) [27].

Let then A be a set of intelligence arguments. We define the concept of being an *accepted argument* and use the notation Nx to say that x is an accepted argument. The accepted arguments

form a subset of A , which we shall say corresponds to the hypothesis space in traditional analysis. Intuitively, to say that x is an accepted argument is to say that we hold for true the hypothesis in x , and that the evidence in x supports the hypothesis under the interpretation given by x .

Then, to say that there is an alternative hypothesis, we suggest here, is to say that whenever x is an accepted argument, then there is another argument y in A , not necessarily accepted, that has the same evidence but another (alternative) hypothesis than x . Similarly, to say in terms of intelligence arguments, we suggest, that evidence is re-evaluated is to say that given an accepted argument x , there must be second argument $y \in A$, not necessarily accepted, such that x and y have the same hypotheses but different evidence.

Define the two binary relations E and H on sets of intelligence arguments such that Exy whenever x and y have the same evidence, respectively Hxy whenever x and y have the same hypotheses. Then we can formalize the two principles in the following definition.

Definition 1 (Two Principles of the Analysis of Competing Hypotheses). Let A be a set of intelligence arguments with predicates N , E , and H defined as above. Then we say that

- A adheres to the principle “Prevent the analyst from premature closure on a particular explanation or hypothesis” [22], (for every accepted intelligence argument x , there must be at least a second argument with the same evidence and a different hypothesis), whenever

$$\forall x \in A(Nx \rightarrow \exists y \in A(Exy \wedge \neg Hxy)). \quad (2)$$

- A adheres to the principle “Ask what evidence is not being seen but would be expected for a given hypothesis to be true. Is denial and deception a possibility?” [22] (for every accepted argument, there must be at least a second argument with the same hypothesis, but with different evidence.), whenever

$$\forall x \in A(Nx \rightarrow \exists y \in A(\neg Exy \wedge Hxy)). \quad (3)$$

Definition 1 formalizes the two principles from the analytic tradecraft we want to incorporate into our analysis. With this concept, we can force a set of intelligence arguments to contain enough intelligence arguments to include also intelligence arguments with alternative hypothesis, and intelligence arguments with previously unseen evidence.

4.4.1 Representing Cyber Attribution in AMBARGO. Recall the setting from Section 4.2 with a forensic sample f and an attribution model $C = C_1, \dots, C_k$ with k clusters corresponding to the patterns of k known APT:s. Our task is to turn such matrices into intelligence arguments. In other words, we need to figure out what in the classification setting counts as evidence, interpretation, hypothesis, and evaluation in the intelligence arguments setting. This is a task with much freedom of choice, and we present here one possibility.

It seems natural that the classes C_1, \dots, C_k should correspond to the hypotheses, since we are looking for an answer to the question of which APT was behind the forensic sample under investigation. The evidence component of the intelligence argument should, also naturally, represent the forensic sample itself.

In Section 4.2, we saw that evidence (forensic matrix) was mapped to the hypotheses (candidate attributed APTs) via an aggregation of similarity scores f_{ij} . The aggregation was made per topic. This can be mimicked in AMBARGO by letting the rows (*topics*) of the forensic matrices be translated into the second component x_2 of the intelligence arguments (i.e., the interpretation of evidence).

We note here that the state-of-the-art additive approach assigns exactly one candidate cluster C_j to each pair (f, i) where f is a piece of evidence (forensic sample) and i is an interpretation (e.g., malware family), via the cosine similarity aggregation of the information in the topic vectors,

where the cosine similarity by design picks exactly one candidate hypothesis. Thus, with some abuse of notation, the state-of-the-art approach would translate the evidence-interpretation pair (f, i) to exactly one intelligence argument (f, i, C_j, r) where r is the aggregated similarity score between f and C_j with respect to topic i . (This illustrates that the additive approach does not adhere to the first principle in Definition 1, supporting representation of alternative hypotheses).

We define AMBARGO differently, for ensuring that the criteria in Definition 1 are met. For each pair (f, i) of evidence and interpretation, we create one intelligence argument for *each* candidate hypothesis: $(f, i, C_1, r_{i,1}), \dots, (f, i, C_k, r_{i,k})$, where i ranges over all topics. As a consequence, for any intelligence argument translated in this way, there are alternative intelligence argument in the sense of Definition 1. We formalize this intuition in the next definition.

Definition 2 (AMBARGO Translation). Let $P = (F, K_1, \dots, K_k)$ form a sequence of matrices of the same shapes. (F may be called the forensic matrix, and K_1, \dots, K_k candidate target matrices). We say that a set A of intelligence arguments is a translation of P if there is a mapping β such that for every entry f_{ij} in F and every index $1 \leq h \leq k$, there is an intelligence argument $(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) \in A$ such that

- (1) $\beta(x_1) = F, \beta(x_2) = i, \beta(x_3) = h, \beta(x_4) = f_{ij}$
- (2) the two properties in Definition 1 hold for A

The result of a translation is a set of intelligence arguments. It is the second requirement in Definition 2 that makes the integration of traditional intelligence analysis possible. It forces the translation to contain arguments that contain alternative hypotheses and evidence.

4.4.2 The AMBARGO Integral. The AMBARGO integral is defined using the Choquet integral on sets of intelligence arguments. As described in Section 3.3, based on a support vector (here, a forensic evidence), the Choquet integral induces a set of capacities over which the integral is computed. In the definition of the AMBARGO integral, we take into account all evidence that is present in the forensic matrix (i.e., all possible interpretations of the forensic matrix). It is this way the AMBARGO integral simulates the human analysts' ability to re-visit evidence. Let $P = (F, K_1, \dots, K_k)$ be as in Definition 2, and let A be the translation of P . If $x = (e, t, h, r) \in A$ for some evidence e and interpretation t , then we say that x *supports* the hypothesis h . Define the set S^h such that $S^h = \{x \in A | x \text{ supports } h\}$.

We shall define the AMBARGO Integral with respect to each interpretation separately. This corresponds to how the probabilistic and fuzzy approaches treat topic vectors separately. Define therefore, for all interpretations/topics t , the set $S[t] \subseteq A$ of all arguments with interpretation t such that

$$S[t] = \{(e, t, h, r_{th}) \in A | \text{for some } e \text{ and } h\},$$

$S[t]$ is called the *total support with respect to interpretation t* . In our use case, $S[\text{malware}]$ would be all the arguments with the topic/interpretation malware. The *total support for hypothesis h* with respect to the interpretation t is the subset $S_h[t] = S[t] \cap S^h$, corresponding to all evidence that could count as support for h .

AMBARGO applies the Choquet integral on the (total) support as described in Section 3.3. In order to apply the Choquet integral, the (total) support vector needs to be ordered in descending order.

The *ordered total support* $\bar{S}_h[t]$ with respect to interpretation t and hypothesis h is the permutation of elements $s_{(1)}, s_{(2)}, \dots, s_{(m)}$ in $S_h[t]$ ordered in descending magnitude with respect to their fourth terms x_4 which give the support for the hypothesis. (Recall that each $s \in S[t]$ is a tuple of the form (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)). The *capacity for hypothesis h* and interpretation t is induced from $\bar{S}_h[t]$

in the same way as in Section 3.3. Thus, the capacity is a sequence $A_1 \subseteq A_2 \subseteq \dots \subseteq A_m$, where $A_i = \{s_{(1)}, \dots, s_{(i)}\}$.

Note here the difference between AMBARGO and the fuzzy approach. Whereas the fuzzy integral defines its capacity based on *one* piece of evidence, AMBARGO defines the (total) capacity based on *all available evidence*, in one go. (This is how AMBARGO keeps a record of all seen evidence).

Definition 3 (AMBARGO Integral). Let $P = (F, K_1, \dots, K_k)$ be as in Definition 2, and Let A be the translation of P .

Let for each topic t occurring as a row in F ,

- $\tilde{f}[t]$ be the ordered total support with respect to topic t
- $A_h[t]$ be the capacity for hypothesis h and topic t
- \mathcal{G}_λ^A be a super-additive measure where the atomic weights $\mathcal{G}_\lambda^A(\{s_j\})$, for $s_j \in \tilde{f}[t]$, are induced from the cell (t, j) in the matrix K_h , for some $1 \leq h \leq k$.

The h -AMBARGO integral with respect to topic t and to P is defined as the discrete Choquet integral of $\tilde{f}[t]$ and given by

$$A_t(f, C_h) = \sum_{(i)} \tilde{f}[t]_{(i)} \left(\mathcal{G}_\lambda^A \left(A_h[t]_{(i)} \right) - \mathcal{G}_\lambda^A \left(A_h[t]_{(i-1)} \right) \right). \quad (4)$$

The AMBARGO Integral is applied in the next section for aggregating the evidence in the attribution use case.

5 Use Case: APT Attribution

In Section 4.2, we used an adaption of an APT attribution use case [41] in the development of AMBARGO. In this section, we parameterize the use case and devise a statistical experiment for evaluation of the performance of AMBARGO. We apply the AMBARGO translation and integral on the use case and compare the performance with two other approaches:

- A probabilistic model adapted from ATOMIC [41] which we use as a representative for CTI state-of-the-art approaches using additive measures.
- A fuzzy approach using a super-additive measure. The fuzzy approach is particularly suited for handling ambiguous and incomplete data [17, 18].

Section 5.1 sets up the statistical experiment and describes both forensic sample generation and the simulated workflow where the defender consumes the forensic samples in the process of attributing them to potential APTs. In Section 5.2, we describe the additive and fuzzy solutions to the attribution problem. In Section 5.3, we describe how the AMBARGO translation and integral are used for solving the attribution task. AMBARGO is compared with the additive probabilistic and the super-additive fuzzy approaches in Section 5.4, using both the traditional performance metrics and a customization of those for better evaluation of the requirements of the analytic tradecraft. In Section 5.5, we investigate the robustness of our experimental results by checking the performance of the approaches while varying key components of the use case description. In Section 5.6, we investigate whether the findings in the test results depend on the additivity property, or whether they in fact depend on the particular choice of representative. For this, we make a comparison on a large-scale dataset of AMBARGO with seven additional state-of-the-art additive advanced ML algorithms which also are state-of-the-art in cyber security classification applications [2, 59]. Section 5.6 tests also scalability, and 5.7 tests real-world applicability of AMBARGO.

5.1 Experiment Setup

APT threat actors have several stealth tactics to their disposal [26], which are deployed with the purpose of increasing the ambiguity and uncertainty on the part of the defender [26]. Our experiments explore the performance of the additive and super-additive approaches under assumptions of different levels of ambiguity in the evidence on which attribution of the APTs is made. To distinguish between the levels, we call them *confident*, *concealing*, and *deceptive* threat actor behaviors. (This corresponds roughly to the three modes of attacker moves discussed by Heckman et al. [26]: Unwitting, Denial, and Deception).

In the *confident* behavior, we assume that stealthy tactics are only minimally deployed. The second level of ambiguity, *concealing*, corresponds to use of stealthy tactics where the threat actor may be concealing their activities. In the third level, *deceptive*, the threat actor takes more active measures to inject ambiguity into to defender's minds and operations.

Our assumption is that the confident behavior produces the least ambiguous evidence, while the concealing tactics produce more ambiguity, and the deceptive tactics produce the most ambiguous evidence. In the practical setting of our experiments, we simulate the notion of degrees of stealthiness and ambiguity in evidence by controlling the overlap of TTPs and IOCs over the APTs, as seen by the defender. We inject overlap by increasing the likelihood that the APT trace simulation models produce overlapping traces (IOCs and TTPs). In the evaluations of our experiments, we also present a metric for measuring the overlap. (It should be noted that this is a simplistic model of ambiguity. While overlap in traces leads to ambiguity, real stealth tactics produce much more intricate uncertainty in the traces).

The scenario has the following properties

- The attribution model contains nine clusters C_1, \dots, C_9 . (thus, nine known APT:s)
- Forensics is analyzed with respect to three topics (malware, industry, and motive). Each topic has 10 members
- A forensic sample is a collection of 100 IOCs drawn randomly from the three topics
- For each cluster C_i , three sets of forensic samples F_i^0, F_i^1, F_i^2 , generated respectively in the confident, concealing, and deceptive modes of operation.

We assume that the clusters C_1, \dots, C_9 have been obtained by clustering of a large number of forensic samples of the confident kind. To the forensic sample and to each cluster we associate matrices \mathbf{f} , and C_1, \dots, C_9 , as defined in Section 4.2.

In order to compare the approaches, we generate forensic samples based on the distributions induced by the matrices C_1, \dots, C_9 and test how well the three approaches to attribution can classify the samples with respect to nine classes of known APT behaviors. The interesting aspect of the experiment is to compare how the approaches perform under the three assumptions of stealthy threat actor behavior: confident, concealing, and deceptive.

5.1.1 Generation of Forensic Samples. We generate forensic samples for each APT_i under the three assumptions of stealthy tactics: confident, concealing, and deceptive. The difference lies in the statistical models generating samples of each mode. As we take the view of the defender, each forensic samples should be understood as containing the TTPs and IOCs that the defender has been able to discern through analysis. The exact design choices, between 6 and 9 discernible IOCs/TTPs per forensic sample, was made based on the MICTIC approach to cyber attribution [66], where traces with 6 IOCs are considered sufficient for high quality attribution. The design choices were further optimized for generating traces with varying overlap of the IOCs over the APTs.

For each APT_i , randomly pick two malware terms out of the ten in the topic malware. These two terms correspond to APT_i 's preferred set of malware (typical for the assumption of confident

$$\text{confident} = \begin{array}{c|cc} & 0 & 1 \\ \hline 0 & 0.8 & 0.2 \\ \hline 1 & 0.8 & 0.2 \end{array} \quad \text{concealing} = \begin{array}{c|cc} & 0 & 1 \\ \hline 0 & 0.4 & 0.6 \\ \hline 1 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{array} \quad \text{deceptive} = \begin{array}{c|cc} & 0 & 1 \\ \hline 0 & 0.2 & 0.8 \\ \hline 1 & 0.2 & 0.8 \end{array}$$

Fig. 2. State transition matrices for determining the toolset use (malware, industry, motive) for each of the modes of operation for an APT in the use case. State 0 corresponds to use of preferred toolset (typical for confident tactics) and state 1 corresponds to the alternative toolsets more used in deceptive tactics.

behavior). Let us denote the set by $mal_i(0)$. Form also $mal_i(1)$ by picking three random malware terms. The malware in $mal_i(1)$ correspond to the APT_{*i*}'s alternative set of malware (for the more stealthy tactics). $mal_i(0)$ and $mal_i(1)$ may intersect by random. The reason for picking three terms in state 1, is to increase the chance of picking terms that overlap with other APT:s, thereby as a result also increasing the ambiguity of the piece of evidence presented by the (possibly overlapping) malware term.

Similarly form sets $ind_i(0)$ and $ind_i(1)$ for APT_{*i*}'s preferred and alternative targeted industry, and the sets $mot_i(0)$ and $mot_i(1)$ for the group's preferred and alternative potential motives. (Here of course, the defender perspective becomes clear in that we discuss potential motives. The group itself is presumably clear on its motives).

To generate a forensic sample, create 100 IOCs by repeating 100 times: first choose a state $s \in \{0, 1\}$. Then randomly pick one malware term from $mal_i(s)$, one industry term from $ind_i(s)$, and one motive term from $mot_i(s)$. Depending on the random state, each forensic sample will thus contain random counts of between 6 and 9 distinct IOCs. Each forensic sample is transformed into a forensic matrix, using the principles given in Section 5.1.

The (hidden) state s is determined via a Hidden Markov Model describing the threat actor's mode of operation (confident, concealing, and deceptive). In the non-deceptive (confident) mode, the group should stick mostly to the preferred malwares in $mal_i(0)$, the preferred industry and the preferred motive. This assumption is reflected in the state transition matrix called *confident* in Figure 2. Similarly, we reflect in the transition matrices *concealing* and *deceptive* that the group uses more of the alternative tools when they are concealing, and that they predominantly use the alternative tools when they are acting deceptively.

We generate 100 forensic matrices for each APT and for each mode of behavior to be classified by our attribution approaches in the following experiments. Cluster matrices for known APTs are generated using the models for confident modes of operation. (This particular design choice implies that defenders are more likely to have seen and analysed the attackers' preferred tools).

5.2 Additive and Fuzzy State-of-the-art Solutions to Attribution

In this section, we implement the probabilistic additive and fuzzy approaches for addressing the use case APT attribution problem.

5.2.1 Additive Attribution. We describe here attribution based on an additive measure. In Mandiant's probabilistic approach [41] the distance from \mathbf{f} to the clusters is defined in two steps. Recall the representation of forensic samples and cluster as matrices where each row corresponds to one topic (e.g., Equation (1)). First, the topic vectors in \mathbf{f} , i.e., the rows in the forensic matrices, in \mathbf{f} are compared with corresponding topic vectors in the cluster matrices C_1, \dots, C_9 , using the so-called *cosine distance*. Since there are three topics, we get a similarity vector $S_{f,j}$ with three terms

$$S_{f,j} = [S_f(t_1, C_j), S_f(t_2, C_j), S_f(t_3, C_j)].$$

where $S_f(t_i, C_j)$ is the distance (S for Similarity) from topic vector i to the corresponding vector in C_j . For example, if the topic is *malware*, $S_{f,j}(\text{malware})$ is the distance from the malware vector in

\mathbf{f} to the malware vector in cluster C_j :

$$S_f(\text{malware}, C_j) = \left| f[\text{malware}] - C_j[\text{malware}] \right|_{\cosine}.$$

We define $S(\mathbf{f})$ as the *similarity matrix* obtained from stacking the $S_f(t_i, C_j)$.

$$S(\mathbf{f}) = \begin{bmatrix} S_1(f, C_1) & S_2(f, C_1) & S_3(f, C_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ S_1(f, C_9) & S_2(f, C_9) & S_3(f, C_9) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The second step in defining the distance between the forensic sample \mathbf{f} and the clusters consists in aggregating the terms of the similarity vector $S_{f,j}$ into one single value s_j for each column j . Attribution is then defined as the cluster C_j for which s_j is the maximum among s_1, \dots, s_9 , which represents the minimum distance. Mandiant uses a weighted average to combine each row j in $S(\mathbf{f})$ into the single value $s_j(f)$. The weights may be determined, as in the case of Mandiant, via machine learning on historical data, or otherwise.

To summarize, the additive state-of-the-art approach to attribution of a forensic sample \mathbf{f} is given by finding the maximum similarity score of $s_j(f)$ for $j = 1 \dots 9$:

$$a_P(f) = \operatorname{argmax}_j s_j(f) = \operatorname{argmax}_j \sum_i w_i \cdot S_f(t_i, C_j). \quad (6)$$

5.2.2 Fuzzy Attribution. The super-additive fuzzy approach to attribution can be applied directly on the matrices \mathbf{f} and C_1, \dots, C_9 , derived as above for the additive approach. Instead of using additive measures, such as probability and the cosine distance, we here use the super-additive fuzzy integral, as it was defined in Section 3.3.

The main contribution of the fuzzy integral in this setting is that it does not assume independence between the values in \mathbf{f} , in other words, it does not assume that the values in \mathbf{f} have been obtained by observing non-ambiguous sources of information. The assumption of non-ambiguous sources of information is too strong for the setting of intelligence analysis [13], since ambiguity in evidence cannot be ruled out (considering the ambiguity in forensic malware analysis, and that it is not in the interest of the threat actor to leave non-ambiguous traces). In our running example, the fuzzy approach captures the possible interaction between observations of PlugX and gh0stRAT, where the evidence supporting PlugX also may support gh0stRAT, due to ambiguity in the malware analysis. (In the probabilistic additive approach, increased support for one hypothesis instead *decreases* support for competing hypotheses).

Attribution in the sense of super-additive measures of the forensic sample \mathbf{f} with respect to each C_j in C_1, \dots, C_9 is done by applying the fuzzy integral on \mathbf{f} in the way we defined in Section 3.3. Where the state-of-the-art probabilistic approach forms the similarity matrix $S(\mathbf{f})$ (Equation (5)), the fuzzy approach instead obtains a corresponding *fuzzy matrix* $H(\mathbf{f})$ by applying the fuzzy integral on each topic vector $f[t]$.

Let therefore C_j be one of the cluster matrices, $\tilde{f}[t]$ be the permutation in descending order of $f[t]$ and let A_1, \dots, A_m be its induced capacity. Define the super-additive measure \mathcal{G}_λ^j on the sets A_i of the capacity, for some $\lambda > 0$, and where the atomic measure $\mathcal{G}_\lambda^j(\{S_k\})$ is obtained from the entry in C_j in the t th row and k th column. Then, the fuzzy integral gives a value $H_t(\mathbf{f}, C_j)$ describing the contribution of the forensic evidence in $f[t]$ to the hypothesis C_j :

$$H_t(f, C_j) = \sum_{(i)} \tilde{f}[t]_{(i)} \left(\mathcal{G}_\lambda^j \left(A[t]_{(i)} \right) - \mathcal{G}_\lambda^j \left(A[t]_{(i-1)} \right) \right). \quad (7)$$

The values $H_t(f, C_j)$ form the fuzzy matrix $\mathbf{H}(f)$ with rows corresponding to the clusters C_1, \dots, C_9 and columns corresponding to topics t :

$$\mathbf{H}(f) = \begin{bmatrix} H_1(f, C_1) & H_2(f, C_1) & H_3(f, C_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ H_1(f, C_9) & H_2(f, C_9) & H_3(f, C_9) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

We form similarly to (Equation (6)) a score for each topic row in $H(f)$ by

$$h_j(f) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot H_f(t_i, C_j). \quad (9)$$

The attribution of f , denoted $a_F(f)$ with respect to the Fuzzy integral is given by

$$a_F(f) = \operatorname{argmax}_j \sum_i w_i \cdot H_f(t_i, C_j).$$

Note that we use weighted average for aggregation in both the state-of-the-art additive probabilistic and the super-additive fuzzy attribution procedures. The difference between the two approaches is the use of the additive similarity measure in the probabilistic case and the super-additive measure in the second case.

In the ensuing experiments, it will be of interest to note that the probabilistic approach, with its additive measure, assumes no interaction between the observed IOCs, i.e., that there is no ambiguity in the observations of the evidence. The fuzzy approach, using the super-additive measure, assumes instead that there is interaction between the observations. I.e., the fuzzy approach takes into account that the observation of one piece of evidence can contribute as support to several different hypotheses, due to potential ambiguity in evidence.

5.3 AMBARGO Solution to Attribution

In this section, we use the AMBARGO translation to derive a set of intelligence arguments from the forensic matrices and the attribution model we defined in Section 5.1. Let A be a set to be successively populated with intelligence arguments. According to Definition 1, each forensic matrix \mathbf{f} gives rise to a number of intelligence arguments $x \in A$ such that the first term x_1 in x corresponds to \mathbf{f} . Each candidate attributable APT corresponds to a hypothesis in the intelligence arguments. Thus, for each forensic matrix \mathbf{f} , we get nine templates of intelligence arguments—one for each candidate hypothesis. Each row in the matrix \mathbf{f} corresponds to one interpretation of the evidence. There are three rows, so each \mathbf{f} gives rise to 9 times 3 arguments (APTs and interpretations). Thus, we have for each \mathbf{f} , 27 arguments of the form (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) where x_1 corresponds to \mathbf{f} , x_3 to one of the APT:s, and x_2 to one of the rows in \mathbf{f} . Finally, x_4 is the entry in the cell of \mathbf{f} in the row corresponding to x_2 and the column corresponding to x_3 , for each argument formed from \mathbf{f} .

Thus, in summary, every forensic matrix \mathbf{f} induces a set A of 27 intelligence arguments.

Then, the AMBARGO integral with respect to a forensic matrix \mathbf{f} is applied on the set A of intelligence arguments induced by \mathbf{f} , according to (Definition 3) for solving the attribution problem. Where the fuzzy approach forms the Fuzzy matrix $\mathbf{H}(f)$ and the additive approach form the similarity matrix $\mathbf{S}(f)$, we form the AMBARGO matrix $\mathbf{A}(f)$

$$\mathbf{A}(f) = \begin{bmatrix} A_1(f, C_1) & A_2(f, C_1) & A_3(f, C_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ A_1(f, C_9) & A_2(f, C_9) & A_3(f, C_9) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where $A_i(f, C_j)$ is the AMBARGO integral of f with respect to cluster C_j , given in Definition 3.

$$A_i(f, C_j) = \sum_{(i)} \tilde{f}[t]_{(i)} \left(\mathcal{G}_\lambda^A \left(A_j[t]_{(i)} \right) - \mathcal{G}_\lambda^A \left(A_j[t]_{(i-1)} \right) \right). \quad (11)$$

In order to derive the attribution of the forensic sample \mathbf{f} , we use the weighted average, with respect to each hypotheses to find the cluster with maximum value

$$a_A(\mathbf{f}) = \operatorname{argmax}_j \sum_i w_i \cdot A_{t_i}(\mathbf{f}, C_j).$$

Note that the use of a weighted average is similar to both the fuzzy and probabilistic approaches. The only differences between the approaches lie in how the entries in the Similarity $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f})$, Fuzzy $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{f})$, and AMBARGO $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{f})$ matrices were computed (Equations (5), (8), respectively 10).

Observe in formula (11) the resemblance of the expression with the Choquet value defined in formula (9). The difference is that AMBARGO defines its measure on the set A which contains *all* available evidence, with the consequence that potentially different interpretations of the evidence can weigh in into the integral value. This is facilitated by the use of intelligence arguments that were constructed to include all interpretations of all available evidence.

5.4 Statistical Experiment: AMBARGO vs. State-of-the-art

We compare the three approaches using the experimental setup from Section 5.1. The suitability of the approaches with respect to both ambiguity and the analytic tradecraft are assessed using adapted metrics we devise below. We can thus illustrate that the state-of-the-art probabilistic approach with additive measures has a diminishing performance, with respect to confidence in attribution, as we introduce more ambiguity under the three assumptions of APT behavior. Moreover, the experiments show that AMBARGO performs better than both the additive and the fuzzy approaches.

In order to measure the increase of ambiguity depending on the APT's stealthy behavior (confident, concealing, and deceptive), we deploy a proxy measure for ambiguity that measures the overlap of hypotheses over the evidence. I.e., the metric *overlap* measures the average number of hypotheses supported by each piece of evidence. In the robustness test, we assume that the APT:s behave deceptively, and we vary other parameters.

5.4.1 Classification Performance. In this section, we compare the three approaches using four common performance measures: *recall*, *accuracy*, *precision*, and *F1-score*. **Accuracy (ACC)** measures the proportion of true attributions out of the total number of attributions. **Precision (PPV)** measures the proportion of true attributions out of all attributions, and represents how well the algorithm can avoid false attributions.

$$\text{ACC} = \frac{\#(\text{True Attributions})}{\#(\text{Attributions})}, \quad \text{PPV} = \frac{\#(\text{True Attributions})}{\#(\text{True Attributions}) + \#(\text{False Attributions})}. \quad (12)$$

Recall (TPR) measures the effectiveness of the algorithm as the proportion of true attributions out of all actual forensic samples. The F1 score (F1) summarizes both aspect of our use case: algorithm efficiency (Recall) and cyber attributions capability (precision and accuracy).

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{\#(\text{True Attributions})}{\#(\text{Forensic samples})}, \quad \text{F1} = 2 \times \frac{\text{PPV} \times \text{TPR}}{\text{PPV} + \text{TPR}}. \quad (13)$$

Evaluation of tests. We note in Figure 3 first that the overlap metric increases as the APT behavior increases in stealthiness (i.e., goes from confident to concealing, and from concealing to deceptive),

Fig. 3. The x-axis represents the combinations of approaches (additive) Probabilistic, Fuzzy, and Ambargo, with the assumptions of APT stealth level (Confident, Concealing, and Deceptive). The figure shows the scores of the combinations *w.r.t* recall (TPR), accuracy (ACC), precision (PPV), and F1-score (F1). The overlap line indicates that ambiguity/overlap varies depending on stealthiness. Note that AMBARGO performs much better than the other two under the assumption of deceptive APT behavior.

indicating increased ambiguity in the evidence as assumed stealthiness increases. The four performance measures indicate that the three approaches perform equally well under the assumptions of confident and concealing APT behavior. However, under the assumption of deceptive behavior, all three approaches decline in performance. Note though that AMBARGO is considerably less affected by the increased ambiguity.

For cyber attribution to be effective, it is important that assessments are made with high confidence and accuracy. Without that, the deterrent effect of cyber attribution would potentially decrease [9]. Without high accuracy and precision, there is potential high costs in connection with acting on incorrect attributions [42]. Precision gives an indication of how well the algorithm identifies the correct attribution and avoiding costly false attributions (False Positives). Accuracy gives a measure of how well the algorithm both identifies the true culprit and confidently discard those APTs that should not be accused of an attack (in some particular instance). We note in Figure 3 that all three approaches perform well in these respects.

One of the motivations with CTI is to automate tedious human intelligence, for which a good metric is *recall*. Recall gives an indication of how effective the algorithm is in attributing the right APT. We note that all three approaches have high recall. The F1 metric gives a combination the three other metrics. F1 combines the metrics that are important for cyber attribution and the metric *recall* that is more important for assessing algorithmic performance.

5.4.2 *Performance Measures Suitable for the Analytic Tradecraft.* The previous subsection showed high performance of all three approaches in the attribution task, with a noticeable advantage for AMBARGO with respect to deceptive APT behavior. In this section, we devise three alternative metrics with which it is possible to distinguish the three approaches further, in particular with respect to suitability for intelligence analysis. We discuss each metric below.

Confidence in Attribution. One aspect of the low quality of CTI is that the algorithmic results are generally of low confidence. CTI reports from commercial vendors using quantitative algorithms are as a consequence generally quite vague in their assessment of high-level intelligence products such as cyber attribution. To show that AMBARGO has the potential to improve the CTI product

quality, we devise a metric for attribution strength called CONF. CONF is an adaption of the Recall metric we used in the previous section. Instead of just counting the number of correct attributions, we take the average of the likelihoods of the predicted hypotheses (i.e., attributions). Let F be the set of forensic samples. For the discussion, let $D(f) = (x^1, \dots, x^9)$ be a descending ordered list of labels of APTs standing for the prediction made by either of the approaches such that x^1 is the APT that is most likely to have generated the forensic sample f .

$$\text{CONF}(i) = \frac{\sum_{f \in F} \text{Score}(x^i)}{|F|}.$$

Define $\text{CONF} = \text{CONF}(1)$. We want CONF to be as high as possible. To enable comparison across experiments, the CONF score is normalized with respect to the number of classes.

Distinctiveness of Attribution. (AHR) In intelligence analysis, it is further important to be able to consider an alternative hypothesis, and to try to find evidence for that hypothesis. We want therefore to be able to find a second strong signal in the analysis besides the main attribution hypothesis. Since we are building an automated tool, however, we want the signal to be strong but not as strong as the main hypothesis. The attribution is thus the clearest when the confidence in the alternative hypothesis is relatively smaller. Therefore we devise a metric AHR, that should be as high as possible, based on the ratio between the aggregated confidence of the second best hypothesis and the best hypothesis:

$$\text{AHR} = 1 - \frac{\text{CONF}(2)}{\text{CONF}(1)}.$$

Distinctiveness of Alternative Hypothesis. It is important in intelligence analysis to be able to identify an alternative hypothesis. We suggest a metric that measures the **distinctiveness of the alternative hypothesis (DALT)** with respect to the total confidence in all hypotheses except the best and the second best hypotheses.

$$\text{DALT} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=3}^9 \text{CONF}(i)}{\text{CONF}(2)}.$$

If DALT is low, then the noise from the inferior hypotheses can be said to drown the signal from the second best hypothesis. DALT should thus be as high as possible for enabling the alternative hypothesis to be discerned in the midst of the information contained in the confidence in hypotheses x^3, \dots, x^9 .

Evaluation of Experiment with the adapted metrics. Note first that for CONF in (Figure 4), the probabilistic approach has a very high confidence under the assumption of confident behavior. However, under the assumptions of concealing and deceptive modes of operation, the confidence in the attribution markedly decreases.

AMBARGO has a high confidence in attribution under all three stealth assumptions. In particular AMBARGO's confidence in attribution is markedly higher than both other approaches' under the assumption of deceptive behavior.

From this, we can conclude that AMBARGO is better suited than the additive approach for handling ambiguous evidence. One possible explanation of the declining performance of the probabilistic approach is that, as a consequence of its additive measure, it assumes that the hypotheses are independent. That the fuzzy approach also has a declining performance as more ambiguity is introduced can be explained by the fact that the ambiguity in our use case depends on an ambiguity in the inference, as described earlier in the article. Fuzzy measures are more suited for applications where there is ambiguity in the input data (e.g., the sensor data).

Fig. 4. Results from the experiment here evaluated with the adapted metrics for suitability for intelligence analysis. The x-axis represents combinations of approach and stealth tactic (confident, concealing, deceptive). CONF gives attribution strength, while AHR and DALT convey how well an alternative hypothesis can be discerned. The overlap line indicates that ambiguity increases with increased stealthiness. Note that AMBARGO has a high confidence in attribution (CONF) also under the assumption of deceptive behavior, where the other approaches decline in performance.

Considering the metrics for distinctiveness, AHR and DALT, one may initially presume that the probabilistic approach would perform better than AMBARGO, since AMBARGO is defined to take all evidence into account when aggregating, thus also seemingly irrelevant information. However, as we can see in Figure 4, AMBARGO trails only marginally behind the probabilistic approach in these aspects. That AMBARGO potentially ingests more noise, may be considered a tradeoff for achieving the larger advantage in terms of the metric for confidence in attribution (CONF). Below, we will also see experiments where AMBARGO improves over the probabilistic approach also with respect to AHR and DALT.

5.4.3 Summary of Experiment. We compared AMBARGO with the state-of-the-art additive approach for automated cyber attribution (based on the description by Mandiant [41]) and the fuzzy approach for handling vague and ambiguous data. When using common performance metrics, it is hard to distinguish the performance between the three approaches, apart from in the most ambiguous case. One might, based on that, be inclined to favor the state-of-the-art probabilistic approach for automated cyber attribution. However, with metrics better suited for intelligence analysis, it becomes apparent that there are differences between the three approaches. Our experiment showed that AMBARGO was better suited to handle ambiguity that can arise due to stealthy APT modes of behavior. We saw in particular, that AMBARGO scored very high in confidence in attribution (CONF) under assumption of deceptive APT behavior, where the other two approaches struggled noticeably. One might ask to what extent the particular setup we used in the use case contributes to our findings. We will investigate that in the next section.

5.5 Robustness of Results

In this section, we test the robustness of the findings in the last subsection. In these experiments, we shall assume that the APTs use only the deceptive mode of operation and instead investigate the impact of other parameters. We also restrict the attention to the probabilistic approach and AMBARGO and perform two experiments:

Fig. 5. Testing the probabilistic approach and AMBARGO for robustness of the results when varying the number of groups. Number of groups varied between 5, 10, 15, and 20. Note when the overlap becomes higher (more ambiguity), the advantage of AMBARGO becomes evident.

- Experiment A. Varying the number of groups. In the base experiment, we had 10 groups. Here, we investigate the effects of having 5, 15, and 20 groups instead. When the number of groups decrease we expect the potential overlapping hypotheses to decrease, leading to less ambiguity. Thus, the state-of-the-art additive approach should benefit from this setting. With increased number of groups, we should see more ambiguity/overlap due to crowding and overlap in the use of tools, which AMBARGO should benefit from.
- Experiment B. Increasing the number of topics. The base experiment had 3 topics. We increase the number of topic and vary with 3, 4, and 6 topics. Since the quality of attribution increases with the number of topics [66], the intuition is that both AMBARGO and the state-of-the-art approach should also show increasing performance.

Results of Experiment A: Varying the number of groups. The results are shown in Figure 5. We see that our intuition was correct, with more groups, the overlap in possible hypotheses per piece of evidence increases. And similarly, with fewer groups, the overlap decreased. We can see that with low overlap, the state-of-the-art approach has a slight advantage in recall, but as the ambiguity increases, AMBARGO performed better with respect to all four metrics, including recall, and in particular AHR and DALT. Note also that both approaches show a declining performance as more ambiguity is introduced, but also that AMBARGO performs relatively better than the probabilistic approach with more ambiguity.

Results of Experiment B: Increasing the number of topics. Figure 6 show the result of Experiment B. Both approaches showed an improved performance with increasing number of topics. AMBARGO shows a clear advantage in confidence in attribution. Note that the line graph, representing ambiguity, does not show a clear trend. This suggests either that increasing the number of topics does not affect ambiguity of the data in the sense we have adopted in the article, or that the increased quality of attribution that can be obtained with increased number of topics may be interacting with the results [66]. However, the experiment shows that AMBARGO performs better also with increasing number of topics.

5.5.1 Alternative Interpretation of Ambiguity. We make a last robustness experiment for exploring whether the interpretation of ambiguity may have an effect on the approaches. In other

Fig. 6. Testing the probabilistic approach and AMBARGO for robustness of the results when increasing the number of topics. We increased number of topics between 3, 4, and 6. This did not have an effect on the overlap/ambiguity, but both approaches show a similar increase in performance with increased number of topics. Again, AMBARGO performs much better than the probabilistic approach with respect to confidence in attribution (CONF).

words, we use the definition of ambiguity for which the fuzzy approach is more suited. We distort the distributions in the cluster matrices, thus generating the clusters according to super-additive measures. The three values of the interaction constant we use in this experiment are 0.0, 0.68, and 1.75 (see Section 3.3, and further on distorted probabilities in [70]). Note that the interaction constant 0.0 yields an additive measure though. Since the fuzzy approach uses a super-additive measure (i.e., in our setting, with an interaction constant of 0.5), the intuition is that the fuzzy approach should perform better than AMBARGO and the state-of-the-art approach.

Figure 7 shows the result of this experiment. Somewhat surprisingly, both AMBARGO and the state-of-the-art approach are unaffected by the variation in convexity. Moreover, the fuzzy approach does not show an improvement in performance relative to the other two approaches. (The lambda parameter in the definition of the fuzzy integral was set to 0.5). We draw three conclusions from this result. The state-of-the-art approach is relatively well equipped to deal with the type of ambiguity that comes from convexity of the probability distributions. Second, the ambiguity that AMBARGO handles better than both other approaches is essentially different in nature from the information ambiguity presented in this experiment. Note that the overlap proxy we have defined for ambiguity is very low, indicating that this experiment did not test the type of inference ambiguity we are investigating. We conclude finally from this experiment that AMBARGO performs robustly also under information ambiguity. Moreover, based on the high CONF scores of AMBARGO, we can also conclude that AMBARGO is more efficient than both the state-of-the-art probabilistic approach and the fuzzy approach with respect to information ambiguity.

5.6 Scalability of AMBARGO

In order to assess the performance of AMBARGO in large-scale settings, we take inspiration from Noor et al. [49] for synthesizing a large-scale attribution dataset based on the ATT&CK Enterprise matrix.³ AMBARGO is here compared with state-of-the-art ML algorithms widely used in the quantitative cyber security literature. This experiment differs from previous sections in

³<https://attack.mitre.org>

Fig. 7. Result of distorting the distribution for which the forensic sample are generated. This tests the robustness with respect to concept of ambiguity. We distort the distributions with which the forensic samples are generated using Sugeno interaction constants 0.0 0.68, and 1.75, thus making the two latter distributions super-additive. None of the approaches were affected by the variation. This indicates that the inference ambiguity studied in the article differs from the information ambiguity concept captured by distorted distributions.

Table 2. Topics and Members in Large-scale Experiment

topic	# members	topic	# members	topic	# members
reconnaissance	57	exploit	147	actions	28
weaponization	46	install	63	malware	596
delivery	163	C2	36	software tools	86

the number of APTs and topics, as well as in using the realistic mappings between TTPs and APTs from ATT&CK (obtained via the Python API⁴). The new dataset contains all 144 APTs recorded in the enterprise matrix, and we define nine topics based on the seven phases in the Cyber Kill Chain together with two topics for *malware* and (*software*) *tools*. The topics are populated with techniques, malware, and tools based on ATT&CK. Table 2 lists all topics and their respective number of members. In this experiment, we thus explore the ambiguity inherent in real data.

Dataset synthesis. For each APT, we extracted the intrusion sets of TTPs and software. For distinguishing between confident, concealing, and deceptive APT behaviors, we note that each technique t is used by a_t groups, for some non-negative integer a_t . Consider the median value M for all such numbers a_t . Techniques t used by more than M groups are classified as more overlapping, and the other techniques as less overlapping. Each intrusion set was partitioned in two sets: one containing the more overlapping TTPs and software and one containing the lesser overlapping ones. For synthesizing a forensic sample, seven IOCs were randomly drawn from the APT's intrusions set. (Again, the number seven here is based on defender point-of-view and practical considerations from Section 5.1). For samples with less ambiguity, i.e., the *confident* mode of operation, we made sure that four IOCs were less overlapping (i.e., they came from the intrusion set partition with less overlapping IOCs); for the concealing samples three IOC were less

⁴<https://github.com/mitre-attack/mitreattack-python>

Fig. 8. Comparison of Precision for AMBARGO and the eight state-of-the-art ML approaches in the large-scale experiment in Section 5.6.

Fig. 9. Comparison of Confidence in attribution for AMBARGO and eight state-of-the-art ML approaches in the large-scale experiment in Section 5.6. Note the decline in confidence for the additive approaches, confirming the findings from earlier experiments.

overlapping; and for the deceptive samples, only one IOC was less overlapping. To synthesize the training set, we created, for each APT, 1,000 forensic samples with seven random TTPs from the respective intrusion set. For each APT, the confident, concealing, and deceptive forensic samples used for testing were drawn according to the principles described above.

Experiment setup. We use Python with packages scikit-learn, xgboost, and Keras, using default model configurations (except as indicated below), to compare AMBARGO with state-of-the-art advanced ML algorithms. The ML algorithms are: **Naive Bayes (NB)**; **K-nearest Neighbors (Knn)** (with 5 neighbors); **Decision Trees (DT)**; **Support Vector Machines (SVM)** (with probabilistic membership scores); **Random Forest (RF)** (with 100 trees); **XGBoost (XGB)**; and **Deep Neural Networks (DNN)** (with 3 dense layers). For comparison, we include also the Probabilistic model from Section 5.2.1. The Probabilistic algorithm and AMBARGO are deployed topic-wise in the same way as in the previous experiments. For the ML approaches, the best results are obtained by treating all TTPs and software as members of one (big) topic and this is how they are evaluated. I.e., the ML models have 1,222 input features (sum of all TTPs and software) and 144 output classes (the 144 APTs). The task is, for all forensic samples f , to attribute f to the APT from whose intrusions set f were most likely drawn (taking into account the level of stealthiness of f).

5.6.1 Evaluation of Experiment. The results of the experiment are shown in Figures 8 and 9. We draw four conclusion from the experiment. First, the difference between the additive approaches and the super-additive AMBARGO we saw in the previous experiment can also be seen in this realistic large-scale experiment. High precision for all approaches, but declining confidence in attribution for the additive advanced ML algorithms as more ambiguity was introduced into the samples. AMBARGO delivers a high confidence even under the assumption of stealthy APT behavior (Figure 9). Second, the probabilistic approach we used for conceptualizing AMBARGO performs comparatively well with other advanced ML algorithms. Third, that AMBARGO has high performance on deceptive samples where the additive approaches perform moderately well, with respect to confidence, indicates a potential that stealthy intrusions may be missed by state-of-the-art ML approaches due to lack in confidence. Threat actors may exploit this weakness in present day’s automated tools for attribution. Fourth, AMBARGO can be applied on realistically large-scale problems.

With respect to processing time, all ML approaches performed better than AMBARGO. The classification of one forensic sample typically had a processing times of fractions of tenths of a second, with SVM being the slowest at 80 milliseconds per sample. While the code was aimed merely for conceptual evaluation and performed on a consumer laptop, we note that for the size of this realistic problem, AMBARGO’s performance was within a second per sample.

Table 3. AMBARGO Topics, Techniques, and Software in Operation Ghost

	Operation Ghost
Ambargo topic	MITRE techniques used in the campaign (and members of topics)
reconnaissance	Acquire Infrastructure: Domains, Develop Capabilities: Malware , Establish Accounts: Social Media Accounts
weaponization	
delivery	Obfuscated Files or Information: Steganography
exploit	Valid Accounts: Domain Accounts
install	Event Triggered Execution
C2	Data Obfuscation: Steganography, Web Service: Bidirectional Communication
actions	
malware	FatDuke, MiniDuke, RegDuke, PolyglotDuke
software tools	PsExec

Fig. 10. Precision scores for Prob and AMBARGO with respect to three types of forensics samples (clear, noisy, ambiguous) for the first Operation Ghost experiment.

Fig. 11. Confidence in attribution scores for Prob and AMBARGO with respect to the clear, noisy, ambiguous forensics samples, in the first Operation Ghost experiment.

5.7 Evaluation of AMBARGO on Real APT Campaign Traces

In this section, we use the same dataset as in Section (5.6) to assess how well AMBARGO performs on traces from the APT29 Operation Ghost campaign,⁵ summarized in Table 3. We evaluate again AMBARGO with respect to precision (which is most important for attribution) and confidence in attribution, We compare with the probabilistic approach, Prob, used earlier as a representative for additive approaches. We make two experiments:

- We compare the approaches' ability to detect ambiguous and noisy traces, by synthesizing three types of forensic samples. One *clear sample*, based on exactly the TTPs recorded for the Operation Ghost campaign; one set of *ambiguous samples* based on only the more overlapping TTPs contained in the campaign; and one set of *noisy samples* where signals from randomly selected TTPs and IOCs not contained in the operation are added.
- The second experiment has five forensic sample types, with respectively one, three, five, seven, and nine TTPs randomly drawn from the campaign. This is to simulate early stages of an investigation, where only little is known about a potential attack.

5.7.1 Evaluation of Experiment. Figures 10 and 11 show the results of the first experiment, with respect to precision and confidence in attribution. It is interesting to note that in both respects, AMBARGO performs better for the ambiguous signal where the additive approach perform moderately well, and that the additive approach perform better on the noisy signal, where AMBARGO performs poorly. This is an indication that AMBARGO may be able to detect with confidence some intrusions that additive approaches may miss.

⁵<https://attack.mitre.org/campaigns/C0023/>

Fig. 12. Precision performance for Prob and AM-BARGO in early stages of an investigation. Forensic samples containing 1, 3, 5, 7, respectively 9 TTPs.

Fig. 13. Attribution confidence for Prob and AM-BARGO in early stages of an investigation. Forensic samples containing 1, 3, 5, 7, respectively 9 TTPs.

In the second experiment (see Figures 12 and 13), we tested how the approaches may be expected to perform with respect to precision and confidence in attribution in early stages of an investigation when only few IOCs and TTPs have been collected. Note that AMBARGO started poorly when there was only one TTP, for quickly coming back and outperform the additive approaches when more TTPs are available. With respect to confidence in attribution, this experiment show that AMBARGO is able to confidently attribute forensic samples with very few TTPs available, and that AMBARGO is markedly better performing than the additive approach in early stages of an intrusion.

6 Implementation

AMBARGO is an algorithmic framework and the work in this article has focused on developing concepts and algorithms. In this section, we address the potential of implementing AMBARGO. We draw material in this section from the insights we gained from implementing AMBARGO for performing the experiments in the previous section.

6.1 Computational Complexity of AMBARGO

The major contributor to the computational complexity of AMBARGO is the super-additive Choquet integration used in computing the AMBARGO matrix (Equation (10)), which in the worst case is exponential in the number of datapoints (the number of intelligence arguments needed for formalizing the problem at hand). We note however that as long as there are only finitely many datapoints (which is the case in any practical application), the underlying Sugeno measure is k -additive, for some finite k , which means that there are algorithms for computing the Choquet integral [8], with lower complexity. As long as the number of input variables is low, the complexity of AMBARGO is determined by the classification step taking the AMBARGO matrix as input, and this step (using the additive Probabilistic model from Section 5.2.1) is polynomial and determined by the number of classes and the number of intelligence argument. This could in practice be cumbersome, but already in applying AMBARGO to the large-scale dataset in Section 5.6, we noted that the complexity can be reduced considerably by removing intelligence arguments with zero weights. Since it is not the focus of this article, we suggest as a future work to research further heuristics for AMBARGO.

6.2 Architecture

In Section 5.3, we used the AMBARGO translation to create a set A of intelligence arguments based on a similarity matrix. The set A was then used by the AMBARGO integral to create the AMBARGO matrix, subsequently used for attribution in the use case. We illustrate this workflow diagrammatically in Figure 14.

For implementing AMBARGO, we suggest the use of an efficient legacy additive component for computing the similarity matrix. In the experiments above, we used a probabilistic model. This

Fig. 14. AMBARGO workflow and architecture. AMBARGO uses a legacy ML workflow to obtain a situational awareness (Similarity Matrix in Equation (5)). From this, we apply AMBARGO translation and integration to obtain an intelligence report.

way, the data ingestion component could also be based on legacy framework for real-time data processing. The AMBARGO translation gives a blueprint for the interface between the similarity matrix and a form that AMBARGO can use, via intelligence arguments.

6.3 Requirements on the Implementation

There are certain common issues in the field of quantitative CTI, which we briefly discuss in this section.

6.3.1 False Positives and False Negatives. As reported in the experiments in Section 5, both precision and recall were high for AMBARGO, implying low scores on both False Positives and False Negatives. AMBARGO scored high even under assumptions of ambiguous forensic samples, and in most cases at least as high as state-of-the-art additive approaches. Thus, from an implementation perspective, AMBARGO will not add to the practical problems with too many false positives and negatives in the operation centers.

6.3.2 Streaming Data. In our proposal for architecture, we suggest to rely on existing ML-based frameworks for building a situational picture (the similarity matrix, Equation (5)). Since most ML algorithms are suitable for streaming data and incremental modeling, an implementation of AMBARGO can thus rely on existing technology for handling streaming and real-time data. Thus, the similarity matrix may be continuously updated both with respect to incremental learning and streaming forensic data. As a consequence, the set of intelligence arguments will have to be continuously updated too. An implementation needs to provide functions both for adding new intelligence arguments and for retracting or updating already produced intelligence argument. An implementation needs also to provide a mechanism for triggering recomputations of the AMBARGO matrix, either based on time-intervals or triggered when the set of intelligence arguments has been updated. Note that, like other streaming data analysis applications, also AMBARGO would have a warm-up phase before classifications become reliable.

6.3.3 Dynamic and Uncertain Environment. Cyber intelligence is dynamic and uncertain. New information may invalidate existing hypotheses. As the implementation should be able to handle streaming data (see the previous paragraph), and since both the similarity and AMBARGO matrices can be continuously and asynchronously updated, adding new evidence and hypotheses should not be an issue. However, an implementation should provide a means for retracting invalidated information. One way of doing this is to retract *all* hypotheses whenever AMBARGO is triggered to recompute the AMBARGO matrix, and to re-assert hypotheses on the basis of the recomputation. In this way, AMBARGO can assure that the dynamics of the environment is reflected.

7 Limitations of AMBARGO

Time critical domains: While efficient algorithms exist for applications with low numbers for variables, the computational complexity of AMBARGO is higher than for the more efficient ML approaches to CTI, which generally are polynomial. This may prevent AMBARGO from being used in real-time sensitive applications (such as for example missile defense, or ransomware attack defense). We saw for realistic problem sizes, in Sections 5.6 and 5.7, however that the time performance for AMBARGO in classifying a forensic sample was less than a second. The worse complexity of AMBARGO need thus not necessarily be a hindering factor for deploying AMBARGO.

Large number of variables: Another possible limitation of AMBARGO is in domains with larger number of variables, and with higher dimensions of the data, than in the cyber attribution domain we have studied in this article. ML-algorithms have been deployed to efficiently analyze and model large volumes of host and network traffic data in intrusion detection, and that should be the preferred choice in such environments. AMBARGO could potentially be deployed if there are domain-specific heuristics that can speed up the algorithm.

Noisy data streams: From the experiments in Section 5.7, we learned that AMBARGO performs better than additive approaches on data streams with ambiguous signals. However, in the presence only of noise, AMBARGO performed poorly in comparison with state-of-the-art ML models.

Automation of repetitive work: Many quantitative approaches to CTI focus on automation of time-consuming and repetitive tasks. AMBARGO is not conceived for, and should not be applied to, such tasks. The aim of AMBARGO is to emulate human reasoning about ambiguous evidence, and the problem size should be similar to what humans can manage. Since our suggested implementation of AMBARGO involves legacy ML frameworks for obtaining situational awareness, it may be possible to utilize such legacy frameworks to transform large problems into suitable sizes.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

We introduced the cyber intelligence analysis approach AMBARGO that incorporates traditional intelligence analysis into CTI for enabling a computational way of leveraging the inherent ambiguity in evidence in the cyber domain. The ability of handling ambiguity means being able to re-evaluate evidence and hypotheses during an investigation, which is an ability usually only ascribed to human analysts. We showed that this integration made AMBARGO capable of outperforming state-of-the-art CTI algorithms in cyber attribution under circumstances with ambiguous evidence and deceptive threat actor tactics.

To support our claims, we devised a use case with cyber attribution and performed both small-scale and large-scale realistic statistical experiments where the performance of AMBARGO was compared with state-of-the-art in attributing synthetic forensic samples based on real data. Interestingly, AMBARGO performed consistently better than state-of-the-art advanced ML algorithm on ambiguous evidence, while on noisy data, the ML approaches performed better than AMBARGO.

We further investigated the potential of implementing AMBARGO and suggested an architecture where an implementation could combine the computational efficiency of ML algorithms for data processing with the robustness of AMBARGO for handling ambiguous evidence.

AMBARGO's ability to handle ambiguous evidence and to emulate human intelligence analysis was shown to outperform state-of-the-art approaches for ambiguous and potentially deceptive threat actor tactics. This makes AMBARGO a candidate to providing a vital and necessary improvement of today's CTI intelligence products. As a future work, we suggest an investigation of how the complementary capabilities of AMBARGO and legacy ML algorithms can be combined into an improved CTI framework.

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